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GGE ON LAWS ROLLING TEXT: STRENGTHENING HUMAN CONTROL OPERATIONALIZATION.

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Policy Statement

At the Group of Governmental Experts (GGE) on Lethal Autonomous Weapon Systems (LAWS), human-machine interaction has been mainly discussed around the term “human control”. These discussions are scarcely reflected in GGE reports, despite a large common ground. Examining the operationalization of human control as presented in the current rolling text [1], we caution against potential weaknesses in the text's search for consensus, while proposing strategies to enhance it.

Background

Although it is central to discussions at the GGE on LAWS, the term “human control” has yet to appear in a GGE Report. The primary phrase used is “Meaningful Human Control” (MHC), which the Stop Killer Robots Coalition defines as the ability to foresee the effects of such weapons, enabling moral and legal judgment (Stop Killer Robots, 2019). Many delegations have adopted this term, making it a central part of the debate. However, some states have rejected it because, in their view, there is no consensus on what MHC entails—delegations sharing this view argue that control depends on the operational context of the weapon’s use, and therefore support the phrase “context-appropriate human control.” Others claim that MHC is not necessary to comply with IHL, or that decision-making about human control requirements should be at the national level.

The first and only mention of “human judgment” in GGE Reports appears in 2019, Paragraph 24, not as a conclusion but as an area for further investigation. Its subparagraph a) refers to delegations arguing for the necessity of human judgment in decisions due to the unpredictability of the operational context and the need for IHL considerations (UNODA, 2019). The 2023 report made notable progress on language related to human control, although it was qualified with “to comply with IHL.” It marked the first time the group had reached a conclusion on this issue. It discusses control over LAWS in Paragraphs 21 through 23: Paragraph 21 addresses control over LAWS effects, Paragraph 22 emphasizes that human-machine interaction must align with IHL principles, and Paragraph 23 states that responsible parties must be able to interrupt, disable, or control the system and its functions when feasible (UNODA, 2023). The trend in 2023 indicates a move toward greater operationalization and substance, even though “human judgment” and “human control” are not explicitly mentioned in the

report.

Currently, negotiations focus on language in the rolling text proposed by the Chairpersonship, where “context-appropriate human judgment & control” appears as a compromise between divergent positions.

Strengthening the rolling text with potentially consensual language while also identifying areas where the current text might be contested is essential. These considerations can clarify the trade-offs needed to maximize substance within political feasibility.

Using the framework proposed by Boulanin et al. (2020) to operationalize human control, our team identified deadlocks in adding language at the 2024 GGE meetings [3]. Our results showed that some delegations oppose including language about: control by the operator; over critical functions [4]; during ‘study’ or ‘pre-R&D’ phases, and ‘use’ phases. We also found caveats regarding control over the effects of LAWS and controlling through human-machine interaction.

Findings

The current rolling text (UNODA, 2025) mentions human control in boxes II (Paragraph 5), III (Paragraphs 4 and 6), and VI (Paragraph 2). Box II discusses control over “use and effects of LAWS.” Box III (Paragraph 4) refers to control over effects during the use phase, and Paragraph 6 uses language from the 2023 report. In Box IV, human control is required throughout the entire life cycle.

Based on our analysis, there are three points where delegations might challenge the current wording: first, human control during the ‘use’ (included in the ‘life-cycle’); second, control over critical functions; and finally, potential caveats regarding the need for control over its “effects,” which probably won't undermine consensus due to the existing language on the subject. Conversely, the rolling text could be improved by incorporating the agreed language on ‘human-machine interaction’ (found in the 2023 Report).

Recommendations

- The Chairperson's team could focus on strengthening and maintaining operationalization rather than using an expression to specify the type of control.
- Delegations could propose building on consensus language from the 2023 report to strengthen the operationalization of human-machine interaction.
- States that have not yet developed their national stance on the operationalization of human control should do so to participate in the debate's nuances fully. The operationalization approach is already implemented by several states in their interventions.

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^[1] By naming the negotiated document “Rolling Text,” the Chairperson's team frames the document as a living working document, in the sense that it is ‘in constant revision.

^[2] Delegations define and analyze ‘judgment’ and ‘control’ in different ways. To better understand positions, in the March 2025 session, the Chairperson asked the following questions: 1) How do human control and judgment relate? 2) When is context-appropriate human control and judgment needed for IHL compliance? 3) Is direct control over critical functions necessary for IHL compliance? 4) Can control be achieved before the use? 5) What specific contextual factors are relevant for context-appropriate human control and judgment? 6) What is the role of external factors?

3] Human control, bias, and risk: Mapping discussions at the 2024 CCW/GGE on LAWS. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15257771>. This fact sheet was presented at the March GGE session and during the NY informal consultations in May.

[4] 'Critical functions' refer to at least targeting and engagement. Some delegations also include 'identifying targets' as a critical function, but it remains contested.

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